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Relationship Between Value Relevance Of Accounting Information And Investment Decision, Evidence From Nigeria Capital Market

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between the value relevance of accounting information and investment decisions in the context of the Nigeria Capital Market. The value relevance of accounting information is crucial for investors as it provides vital data about a company's financial status, aiding in strategic decision-making. However, the quality and relevance of this information can significantly impact its usefulness. This research aimed to assess the value relevance of accounting information and its influence on investment decisions, providing evidence from the Nigerian Capital Market. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. The population for this study consisted of all quoted commercial banks in Nigeria. Available data from the Port Harcourt branch of the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) revealed that there are 15 listed commercial banks in Nigeria. This study utilized primary and secondary sources of data. The findings of this study could offer valuable insights for investors, financial analysts, and other users of financial statements. It was concluded that there is no significant relationship between the reliability of accounting information and dividend per share. Comparability of accounting information does not significantly affect earnings per share while timeliness of accounting information does not significantly affect net assets value per share. The study recommended amongst others that all quoted companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange must as a matter of urgency comply with the preparation of Simplified Investor's Summary Accounts (SISA) with emphasis on accounting information on earnings, book value, dividends and cash flows aside from the mandatory detailed financial statements. This will remove information overload, particularly for nonaccountants and non-financial analysts.

Keywords: Value Relevance of Accounting Information, Investment Decision, Relationship Evidence, Nigeria Capital Market

INTRODUCTION

The importance and relevance of accounting information have become a significant concern for many researchers, leading to numerous studies. Accounting information serves various users, including government agencies for tax purposes and investors for making investment decisions. An accounting information system is an organizational element that gathers, categorizes, processes, analyzes, and communicates decision-making information to a company's external parties (like current and potential

investors, federal and state tax agencies, and creditors) and internal parties (mainly management). According to the “Generally Accepted Accounting Principle” (GAAP), for information to be useful for decision-making, it must have at least four main characteristics: relevance, reliability, understandability, and comparability. Ofurum and Ogbonna (2014) suggest that sufficient accounting information is crucial for the efficient operation of capital markets and a nation’s economic growth. Value relevance of accounting information is the ability of accounting numbers to summarize the information that affects a company's stock price. This is measured by the statistical relationship between accounting information and stock prices.

Despite its importance, accounting information has been criticized by stock market researchers for a number of reasons, including life cycle stage, high technology, fraud, rapidly changing business environment, and increasing conservatism. In Nigeria, there are a number of issues that can lead to accounting information not being useful or relevant, such as fraud, overstating of profits, untimely information, falsified records, and negligence of auditors. For example, in 2006, the accounting scandal of Cadbury (Nig) Plc came to light, which highlighted the need for accountants to develop the skills to identify fraud and mismanagement.

Financial statements are used by quoted and listed companies to communicate with stakeholders. Accounting standard setters and stock market regulators work together to enhance the quality of financial statements and improve the level of financial reporting, in order to ensure transparency. However, there are still widespread cases of poor performance, audit failures, and fraud in Nigeria. For example, in 1957, the managing director of Re Thomas Gerrad & Sons Ltd falsified the accounts for a number of years by altering invoices and introducing non-existing stock. This was done to overstate the company's profits, which could deceive investors. Auditors are expected to detect all forms of fraudulent activity. In summary, the value relevance of accounting information is important, but there are a number of factors that can lead to it being unreliable, such as fraud and negligence. Accounting standard setters and stock market regulators are working to improve the quality of financial reporting in Nigeria, but there is still room for improvement. The financial statement provides information about a company in order to make better decisions for users especially the investors in this instance. It helps to enlighten the users of the accounting information for a better decision towards their future action or plan. The case cited above can discourage an intending investor not to invest his hard-earned money in shares or any investment of any sort. For information to be seen as useful or relevant, it must meet the attributes of accounting information which is opined by “(GAAP)” such as relevance, understanding, timeliness, etc.

Balachandran and Mohanran (2006) in their study noted the relationship between conservatism and the value relevance of accounting information and concluded that there is proof that firms with increasing conservatism see a greater decline in value relevance than firms with decreasing conservatism. Collao. Cueller and Jarne (2006) perform a comparative analysis of the value relevance of reported earnings per share and their components. Their research gives evidence or proof for the value relevance of net earnings per share figure. Therefore, the study fills the gap in the literature by investigating if accounting information is relevant for investment decisions in the Nigeria capital market. For accounting information to be effective, it must be complete, relevant and reliable.

Statement of the Problem

Accounting information, which provides crucial data about a company’s financial status, plays a key role in investment decisions and capital market growth. However, the value of this information is contingent on its quality and relevance to users. Investors rely on this information for share pricing, giving organizations with high-quality information an advantage. To be considered relevant, accounting information must be reliable, comparable, understandable, and timely. However, some accounting information does not meet these standards set by the Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) or the qualifying report standards, which require clarity, specificity, and a clear explanation of the financial statement’s impact. The phrase “True and Fair view”, introduced by the UK 1948 Companies Act and adopted by Nigerian legal and accounting professionals, implies that financial statements should be honest and unbiased. Despite the introduction of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) to

ensure uniformity in global accounting, interpretational differences can hinder their effectiveness. Some organizations or nations have yet to adopt these standards, leading to substandard accounting reporting. The relevance of accounting information is crucial for various stakeholders, including customers, suppliers, lenders, employees, and investors, who base their strategic decisions on this information. However, scandals like Enron and WorldCom in 2002 have raised concerns about the accuracy of company disclosures, leading to a loss of investor confidence and negative impacts on the economy and people's financial well-being. One significant issue is the lack of a unified set of accounting standards across countries, leading to diversity in accounting practices and potential difficulties for foreign investors in the Nigerian capital market. As Ofurum, Egbe and Micah, (2014) suggest, different national accounting standards can hinder the flow of understandable and quality information. The adoption of a common set of global accounting and financial reporting standards, such as the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), can facilitate investment and economic decisions worldwide by providing high-quality, transparent, and comparable information. However, without these common standards, comparing financial information from entities in different parts of the world can be challenging. This study aims to assess the value relevance of accounting information and its impact on investment decisions, specifically in the Nigerian Capital Market.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study was to examine the relationship between the value relevance of accounting information and investment decisions, evidence from Nigeria capital market specifically the objectives were to:

1. examine the relationship between the reliability of accounting information and dividend per share.
2. find out the extent to which comparability of accounting information affects earnings per share.
3. evaluate the effect of timeliness of accounting information on net assets value per share.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of the relationship between the reliability of accounting information and dividend per share?
2. To what extent does comparability of accounting information affect earnings per share?
3. What effect does the timeliness of accounting information have on net asset value per share?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between the reliability of accounting information and dividend per share.
2. There is no significant relationship between the comparability of accounting information and earnings per share.
3. There is no significant relationship between the timeliness of accounting information and net assets value per share.

Significant of the Study

The result of this research will be of immense benefit to various stakeholders that are summed into these broad categories:

- i. Prospective investors in the Nigerian money and capital markets, fundamental and technical analysts, shareholders and investors in both private and public sectors of the economy, creditors and debtors, government and the general public. The study will enable them to assess the benefits available in financial reports and financial reporting.
- ii. Policymakers in the banking industry will benefit immensely from the study as it redirects and refocuses their attention on the significance of financial information in the financial service industry.
- iii. Government at all levels will find this work very interesting as it reveals the extent and the environment that is conducive enough that propel investment climate.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. The population for this study consisted of all quoted commercial banks in Nigeria. Available data from the Port Harcourt branch of the Nigerian Stock

Exchange (NSE) revealed that there are 15 listed commercial banks in Nigeria. This study utilized primary and secondary sources of data. The financial data (DPS, EPS, and NAVPS) because of their nature have been collected from annual reports and accounts of all quoted banks in Nigeria. Questionnaires and interviews were the other instruments employed to collect non-financial data (which are associated with the predictor variable) for this study. They are special forms of correspondence developed to procure authoritative information from a number of people through the medium of well-directed questions and interactions. The annual reports and accounts collected from all quoted banks in Nigeria are highly reliable database instruments for obtaining secondary data since they are audited by external auditors. The research instruments were subjected to content and construct validity. This was ascertained through a collaborative effort by peer and expert approval. In analyzing the data generated for this study and examining the relationship between the criterion and the predictor variables, the Parametric, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique was used. This technique was used because it measures the relationship between the criterion variable(y) and predictor variable (x). It symbolizes the strength (closeness) as well as the direction of the relationship between the two variables. This study examined three major models to measure the possible relationship between the value relevance of accounting information and investment decisions.

Model 1

Based on the perceived functional relationship between the reliability of accounting information and dividend per share, a link is forged between the two variables. Thus, with the functional relationship and the resultant model using the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression method, we have:

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Functional relationship

$$DPS = F(RoAI) \quad (1)$$

Converting this to a linear or stochastic model we have;

$$DPS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RoAI + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

Where β_0 & β_1 are constants, DPS=Dividend per Share, RoAI=Reliability of Accounting Information, ϵ =Error Term or Stochastic term, Apriori expectation= $E(\epsilon) = 0$

Model 2

We can also establish the relationship between the comparability of accounting information and earnings per share. The functional relationship and the resultant model using the OLS regression method is shown below:

Functional relationship:

$$EPS = F(CoAI) \quad (3)$$

Converting this to a linear or stochastic model we have;

$$EPS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CoAI + \epsilon \quad (4)$$

Where β_0 and β_1 are constant, EPS = Earnings per Share, CoAI = Comparability of Accounting Information, ϵ =Error term or stochastic item, Apriori expectation = $E(\epsilon) = 0$

Model 3

Similarly, the relationship between the timeliness of accounting information and net assets value per share can be established. The functional relationship and the resultant model using the OLS regression method is shown below:

Functional relationship:

$$NAVPS = F(ToAI) \quad (5)$$

Converting this to a linear or stochastic model we have;

$$NAVPS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ToAI + \epsilon \quad (6)$$

Where β_0 and β_1 are constant, NAVPS Net Assets Value per Share, ToAI = Timeliness of Accounting Information, ϵ =Error term or stochastic item, Apriori expectation = $E(\epsilon) = 0$

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RESULTS

The analyses begin with the examination of the basic features of the data using descriptive statistics. Mean and Standard deviation were obtained from the studied quoted banks in Nigeria on the dimensions of the predictor as well as the criterion variables.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Predictor Variable

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
RELIABILITY OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION	15	13	15	14.27	.594
RoAI1	15	4	5	4.67	.488
RoAI2	15	5	5	5.00	.000
RoAI3	15	4	5	4.60	.507
COMPARABILITY OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION	15	13	15	13.87	.640
CoAI1	15	4	5	4.60	.507
CoAI2 -	15	4	5	4.67	.488
CoAI3	15	5	5	5.00	.000
TIMELINESS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION	15	14	15	14.27	.458
ToAI1	15	5	5	5.00	.000
ToAI2	15	5	5	5.00	.000
ToAI3	15	4	5	4.27	.458
Valid N (listwise)	15				

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for Criterion Variable

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
DIVIDEND PER SHARE	15	.00	1.75	.4093	.63599
EARNINGS PER SHARE	15	.06	3.33	1.5907	1.06181
NET ASSET VALUE PER SHARE	15	1.13	17.60	9.4060	4.55966
Valid N (listwise)	15				

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The summary of the results as well as their analysis and interpretations, considering the models specified in the methodology and the gathered data are shown in the following sections.

Table 3: RoAI and I)PS Regression Result

Model Summary^a

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.106 ^b	.011	-.065	65624	1.634

a. Predictors: (Constant), RELIABILITY OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION

b. Dependent Variable: DIVIDEND PER SHARE

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.218	4.219		-.289	.777
	RELIABILITY OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION	.114	.295	.106	.386	.706

a. Dependent Variable: DIVIDEND PER SHARE

From table 3 above, the correlation coefficient (R) is 0.106. This shows a very low positive correlation between Reliability of Accounting Information and Dividend per Share. The coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.011. This value is very low and it also confirms the apriori expectation of a positive relationship between Reliability of Accounting Information and Dividend per Share. The low R² of 0.011 implies that 1.1% of the variation in Dividend per Share is actually explained by the Reliability of Accounting Information. The remaining 98.9% is caused by other variables outside the model but covered by the error term. Similarly, the adjusted R² with a value of -0.065 indicates a more reliable coefficient of determination having taken the required degree of freedom into consideration. The negative value of -0.065 indicates a negative relationship between reliability of accounting information and dividend per share. The Durbin Watson Statistics of 1.634 is substantially close to 2.00 and it signifies the absence of autocorrelation in the regression variables.

The variable of Reliability of Accounting Information revealed a low positive coefficient of 0.114 and a statistically significant t-square of 0.386 which means that the reliability of accounting information does not significantly influence DPS. The associated probability value of 0.706 is substantially greater than p=0.005 and signifies no relationship between the Reliability of Accounting Information and Dividend per Share.

Table 4: CoAI and EPS Regression Result

Model Summary^a

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.100 ^a	.010	-.066	1.09637	1.968

a. Predictors: (Constant), COMPARABILITY OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION

b. Dependent Variable: EARNINGS PER SHARE

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.710	6.356		-.112	.913
	COMPARABILITY OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION	.166	.458	.100	.362	.723

a. Dependent Variable: EARNINGS PER SHARE

From table 4 above, the correlation coefficient (R) is 0.100. This shows a very low positive correlation between the Comparability of Accounting Information and Earnings per Share. The coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.010. This value is very low and it also confirms the apriori expectation of a weak positive relationship between Comparability of Accounting Information and Earnings per Share. The low R² of 0.010 implies that 1% of the variation in Earnings per Share is actually explained by Comparability of Accounting Information. The remaining 99% is caused by other variables outside the model but covered by the error term. Similarly, the adjusted R² with a value of -0.066 indicates a more reliable coefficient of determination haven taken the required degree of freedom into consideration. The negative value of -0.066 indicates negative relationship between comparability of accounting information and earnings per share. The Durbin Watson Statistics of 1.968 is substantially close to 2.00 and it signifies the absence of auto correlation in the regression variables.

The variable of Comparability of Accounting Information revealed a low positive coefficient of 0.166 and a statistically significant t-square of 0.362 which means that comparability of accounting information does not significantly influence EPS. The associated probability value of 0.723 is substantially greater than p=0.05 and signifies no relationship between Comparability of Accounting Information and Earnings per Share.

Table 5: ToAI and NAVPS Regression Result

Model Summary^a

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.077 ¹	.006	-.071	4.71778	2.413

a. Predictors: (Constant), TIMELINESS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION

b. Dependent Variable: NET ASSET VALUE PER SHARE

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.518	39.318		-.039	.970
	TIMELINESS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION	.766	2.755	.077	.278	.785

a. Dependent Variable: NET ASSET VALUE PER SHARE

From table 5 above, the correlation coefficient (R) is 0.077. This shows a very low positive correlation between Timeliness of Accounting Information and Net Asset Value per Share. The coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.006. This value is very low and it also confirms the apriori expectation of a weak relationship between Timeliness of Accounting Information and Net Asset Value per Share. The low R² of 0.006 implies that 0.6% of the variation in Net Asset Value per Share is actually explained by Timeliness of Accounting Information. The remaining 99.4% is caused by other variables outside the model but covered by the error term. Similarly, the adjusted R² with a value of -0.071 indicates a more reliable coefficient of determination haven taken the required degree of freedom into consideration. The negative value of -0.071 indicates negative relationship between timeliness of accounting information and net asset value per share. The Durbin Watson Statistics of 2.413 also signifies the absence of auto correlation in the regression variables. The variable of Timeliness of Accounting Information revealed a low positive coefficient of 0.766 and a statistically significant t-square of 0.278 which means that timeliness of accounting information does not significantly influence NAVPS. The associated probability value of 0.785 is substantially greater than p=0.05 and signifies no relationship between Timeliness of Accounting Information and Net Asset Value per Share.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of findings is based on the decision rule which is to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative if the probability value of the z-statistics is less than 0.1 or accept the null and reject the alternative if the probability value is 54 greater than 0.1. Considering the individual coefficients of the explanatory variables, the findings made from the empirical analysis are:

H01: There is no significant relationship between reliability of accounting information and dividend per share.

Based on the t-statistics and associated probability of 0.386 and 0.706 respectively, this study accepts the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant relationship between reliability of accounting information and dividend per share.

H02: Comparability of accounting information does not significantly affect earnings per share.

Based on the t-statistics and associated probability of 0.362 and 0.723 respectively, this study accepts the null hypothesis. Thus, the comparability of accounting information does not significantly affect earnings per share.

H03: Timeliness of accounting information does not significantly affect net assets value per share.

Based on the t-statistics and associated probability of 0.278 and 0.785 respectively, this study accepts the null hypothesis. Thus, the timeliness of accounting information does not significantly affect net asset value per share.

CONCLUSIONS

From the analysis carried out and based on the result of the statistical testing, the conclusion includes:

1. There is no significant relationship between reliability of accounting information and dividend per share.
2. Comparability of accounting information does not significantly affect earnings per share.
3. Timeliness of accounting information does not significantly affect net assets value per share.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are made;

1. Investors should have basic knowledge of business and economics.
2. They should be well informed when making their investment decision.
3. They should not depend on the information from speculators or other co-investors who have a similar interest in the identical phenomenon. Rather they should go through the audited annual reports which provide a mirror of the company's performance, financial position and changes in control of the owners.
4. All quoted companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange must as a matter of urgency comply with the preparation of Simplified Investor's Summary Accounts (SISA) with emphasis on accounting information on earnings, book value, dividends and cash flows aside from the mandatory detailed financial statements. This will remove information overload, particularly for nonaccountants and non-financial analysts.

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